

Technical report

Expert interview and Case study on user journey maps

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This report serves to provide additional information to the paper: An Extension to Archimate: integrating User journeys with Enterprise Architectures. The report provides a practical investigation on specifying user journeys.

Practical investigation: Expert interview & Case study

This document contains a practical investigation of how user journeys and customer journeys are specified in practice. The practical investigation consists of two parts: A) An expert interview with an actual customer journey software vendor, and B) a case study at ContextMSP: A multiservice provider in the banking sector. Although this thesis is scoped on user journeys, we found in the literature that customer journeys are more frequently used, and many practitioners seem not even aware of the difference between the two journeys. Hence, we investigate both user- and customer journey in practice.

To structure the investigation and ensure all important aspects covered, we formulate the following sub-research questions:

***SQ1.1.** What are user journeys and what types of journeys exist?*

***SQ1.2.** What are the elements of a user journey?*

***SQ1.3.** What are the current ways for specifying user journeys?*

***SQ1.4.** How are user journey maps currently supported and applied in the fields of UX design and enterprise architecture?*

To find answers to the SQ's, the expert interview and case study were also structured into questions. To distinct these questions, the expert interview was structured into interview research questions (IRQs) and the case study was structured into case study research questions (CRQs).

1. Expert interview: JourneySoftware

In this section, we investigate the customer journey practice at a customer journey software vendor. Due to privacy regulations, this software is anonymised as JourneySoftware. The *main objective* is to complement and compare the literature results with practical insights from a customer journey software vendor. This helps us in the process of *theory building*, as we gather new requirements or support for existing requirements for our artefact. The software vendor possibly has a different perspective on user-/customer journey maps compared to the literature, has insight in what fields their software is used and has created its own customer journey concepts and notation. Several topics that were covered in our literature review were; user journey characteristics and types of journeys, user journey elements, how user journeys are visualised and applied in practice. Based on these topics, the following *Interview Research Questions (IRQs)* were formulated:

IRQ1. *What types of journeys does JourneySoftware recognise and support?*

IRQ2. *How does JourneySoftware support journeys and improve user experience?*

IRQ3. *What are the applications and fields of practice of JourneySoftware?*

IRQ4. *What concepts are used/recognised by JourneySoftware?*

IRQ5. *What notation is used by JourneySoftware?*

To answer the research questions above, 12 questions were formulated. The interview protocol, along with the answers, can be found in Appendix A. We analysed the results as followed. During the interview, the answers of the interviewee were directly noted and summarized. After the interview, the answers were checked by the interviewee if the answers were correct and complete. There are memo's available of the conversations (just to be certain), but they were unnecessary. For future research, these recordings could be of use (please contact the author in case of interest).

1.1. JourneySoftware

JourneySoftware is a tool that allows organisations to create, analyse and optimize *actual customer journeys*. That said, JourneySoftware has a broader focus than user journeys and does not include planned journeys. However, clients often seem to desire both planned- and actual customer journey practice. To satisfy clients, the implementation of JourneySoftware is often combined with an additional, external planned customer journey tool. Instead of understanding, evaluating and improving *user experience*, customer journey maps are used to improve *engagement*. Where user experience sets focus on how customers feel when going through a process, engagement is more focused at continuously working on the relationship with a customer, triggering customers to become a customer or remain a loyal customer.

1.2. Creating and navigating actual journeys

The journeys created of JourneySoftware are based on actual customer behaviour data (like where customers click on a website) derived from backbone systems. JourneySoftware monitors each individual customer behaviour. However, the specified actual customer journeys do not visualise the behaviour of one single journey but captures multiple customers and uses personas to classify customer types. Covering multiple customer journeys provides an overview and creates the opportunity to manage journeys.

JourneySoftware does not blindly map all behaviour data, but filters on predefined contextual factors. The factors are derived from existing documentation of the client, about their customer flows (preferably planned customer journeys). By recognising a context in actual customer behaviour, the journey and customer goal can be derived from existing documentation or previous behaviour patterns. Knowing the planned journey and goal of an actual journey, business service decisions can be suggested to assist customers in their journey. To suggest service decisions, JourneySoftware uses process mining to map user behaviour and identify bottlenecks. Next, JourneySoftware applies AI to suggest a business service at the bottleneck, a decision based on the knowledge that was derived from earlier behaviour. The company labels this practice as *Journey based decisioning*: improving journeys by applying knowledge from previous journeys (using AI). The

interviewee added that AI driven journey improvement is not yet frequently applied in practice. He argued that due to novelty of deep learning, there is a need for additional research on this topic. Additionally, he added the adoption rate of AI usage is low as people like to stay in control themselves.

1.3. Omnichannel journeys

Instead of supporting multi-channel customer journeys, JourneySoftware supports *Omnichannel* journeys. According to the interviewee, omnichannel goes “one step further” than multichannel journeys. Where multichannel entails that services can be used through different channels, omnichannel entails *synchronous, coordinated* use through different channels. With omnichannel services, a customer can switch from channel to channel and continue the service process or conversation where it stopped. For example, a customer could stop their conversation with a chatbot (channel A) and continue the conversation with a customer service employee (channel B) from the point it ended. To clarify the role of JourneySoftware in the support of omnichannel services, an (abstract) drawing was made by the interviewee, on which we added annotations that summarize the corresponding explanation. The drawing, combined with the annotations, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: JourneySoftware as a Hub-spoke system

The *top layer* shows the different channels a journey can go through. Each individual journey is tracked through an individual ID. By using the ID, JourneySoftware synchronises journeys across different channels, done in the *middle layer*. To synchronise journeys across channels, JourneySoftware has to be integrated with the client’s software that supports/enables these channels. These backbone systems are shown in the *bottom layer*. As JourneySoftware tracks individual journeys across channels (top layer) while communicating with the software that supports these channels (bottom layer), JourneySoftware is seen as a Hub.

1.4. Practical value & usage

In our literature study, we identified three main applications of user journey maps: developing or improving a service or product (i), optimization of journeys (ii) and understanding potential customers to make them customers (*buyer journey*) (iii). The interviewee recognised these practical uses, but added that many customers also apply their software for the sake of:

1. *Keeping customers (post-purchase phase)*. Keeping customers loyal is an important application. Satisfied customers can make their children or friends become customers as well, becoming an ambassador and playing a role in the buyer journey themselves.

2. *Cross-selling or up-selling.* Where cross-selling is getting current customers to use more products/services, up-selling is focused on getting current customers to use more expensive and extensive products/services.
3. *Internal optimisation.* This concerns the processes within a company, streamlining internal processes.

Next to the applications, the fields of practice were also discussed. In the literature study, we identified UX design (i), Enterprise architecture (ii) and Marketing (iii) as fields of practice in terms of user journey maps. The interviewee only recognised *Marketing* as one of the main fields of practice and mentions he misses *customer services* as a big field of practice; helping the customer with a problem or question.

1.5. Used concepts

The customer journey elements of JourneySoftware have also been discussed to get an impression of what terms are used in practice. Although this seems like a validation of our literature-based concepts, this checklist merely serves as an overview of the popular/common concepts that we later consider in the evaluation of the initial requirements list of our artefact. To identify the concepts used by JourneySoftware, the concepts from our literature study were provided to the interviewee. The interviewee then read all concepts and definitions and checked the boxes of each concept that corresponds to their concepts (Appendix A). The results are shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Journeysoftware Concepts used compared to literature

Expert interview: JourneySoftware			
General concepts	Concept used and applied	Journey specific concepts	Concept used and applied
User journey		Touchpoint	*
Customer journey	X	Moment of truth	X
Buyer journey	X	Deviation	
Mapping		Breakpoint	X
User journey map		Initiator	
Customer journey map	X	Trigger	X
Buyer journey map		Goal	X
Journey concept		Time	X
Planned journey	**	Timeline	X
Actual journey	X	Stage	X
Scenario		Channel	X
Persona	X	Trace	
		Experience	X
		Note	
		Opportunity	X
		Lens	

* Used, but with different definition
 ** Recognised but not implemented

Although JourneySoftware uses *Touchpoint* as a concept, it does not mean the same as our definition. Instead of an interaction between customer and service provider, JourneySoftware uses touchpoint to indicate instances of channels. To clarify, they identify websites as a channel, but specific websites (website A, website B) as touchpoints. Additional to the concepts in Table 1, JourneySoftware adds *Proposition* and *Activity type* as concepts. JourneySoftware defines proposition as a product or service the customer is interested in, which equals the Goal concept from our literature study. Activity type entails what the customer is doing (like calculating mortgage costs on a website). Activity here corresponds to our touchpoint concept, meaning this could be a synonym for Touchpoint.

1.6. Used visualisation and notation

During the interview, the interviewee showed an actual customer journey example. A screenshot of this example can be found in Appendix A. The elements of the notation (Appendix A) were discussed and the interviewee showed how these elements are implemented in the example. To create an overview of the implemented concepts, we visualise the elements onto the notation. The result can be found in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: JourneySoftware screenshot with the concepts

The visible concepts are proposition (the *goal* of the customer), *stages*, *channels*, *touchpoints* and *activities*. The journey is visualised from left to right, stages are placed on top of the journey, while channels and specific channels (called Touchpoints by JourneySoftware) are modelled with swimming lanes. At last, experience seems to be absent in terms of emotions, but is indirectly visible in terms of user behaviour which is shown in flow directions and number of IDs that follow those flows. The interviewee added that this is their way to express experience.

1.7. Conclusion – Expert Interview

The interview has provided us with practical insights, acknowledging, contradicting and complementing the results of our literature study. The interview protocol was based on five interview research questions (IRQs), each focusing on a subtopic discussed in our literature review. The discussed topics were: Types of journeys (IRQ1), how the software supports journeys and improves user experience (IRQ2), the applications and user fields of JourneySoftware (IRQ3), used concepts (IRQ4), and notation (IRQ5).

- IRQ 1** As types of journeys, JourneySoftware recognised customer journeys, actual journeys and planned journeys, but were unaware of user journeys. JourneySoftware only supports actual customer journeys but is usually implemented with an external tool to complement JourneySoftware with planned journey maps.
- IRQ 2** To support customer journey maps and improving user experience, JourneySoftware captures individual customer behaviour, gives each journey an ID and creates a cumulative overview of multiple journeys. Additionally, the software contains AI technology that helps to navigate journeys by suggesting business services at specific moments. In contrary to the literature that stated customer journeys are multi-channel with a focus on user experience, JourneySoftware appeared to be omnichannel with a focus on engagement.
- IRQ 3** Concerning the applications of CJ/UJ maps that were found in the literature, JourneySoftware acknowledged that many clients use the software for improvement of products and services (i), journey optimization (ii), and understanding/acquisition of new customers (iii). Additionally, they added that many customers apply their software for *keeping customers loyal* (iv), cross-selling and up-selling (v) and *internal optimisation*. As fields of practice for actual customer journeys, JourneySoftware recognised Marketing as one of the fields but did not recognise architects and UX designers in their clients. Though, the interviewee complemented the list by adding *customer services* as one of their main application fields.
- IRQ 4** Discussing the concepts, the list of concepts from the literature was compared to the concepts used and applied by JourneySoftware. In total, many concepts were acknowledged by JourneySoftware. Remarkably, user journeys, buyer journeys, mapping and deviation were not recognised. Additionally, touchpoint was used but with different semantics (instances of channels). Additionally, they use *activity* as concept what we previously perceived as touchpoint.
- IRQ 5** As notation, JourneySoftware specified a flow of activities going from left to right. Channels were represented in swimming lanes on the left side, while stages were shown on top. Additionally, the journey goal was shown as *proposition* and deviations were shown in numbers (although the term was not a recognised concept). At last, experience was not included in JourneySoftware's notation.

2. Case study: ContextMSP

In chapter 1, we complemented our literature results with practical insights from an actual customer journey software vendor. In this section, we perform a case study at a banking company. The *main objectives* for this case study are complementing and comparing the list of user-/customer journey concepts (i) and investigating journey maps and collaboration among architects and UX designers (ii). This helps us in the process of *theory building* as we gather extra requirements or requirements support for our artefact. For this case study, we partly follow the structure of [1], discussing the case study design, results and conclusion. The introduction and related work on the topic are not discussed as UJ/CJ have been extensively discussed in the literature study.

2.1. Case study design

The case study is held at a multiservice provider (MSP) in the Dutch banking domain. Due to privacy regulations, the MSP is anonymized as ContextMSP. With more than 61.000 active employees and operating in 44 countries across the world, ContextMSP can be considered as a large enterprise. By doing a case study, we aim to observe their user journey and customer journey practice (to complement literature study results) and investigate the collaboration between architects and UX design. Hence, we define our scope the way the results are structured: we focus on terminology (3.2.2.), UJ/CJ practice among architects (3.2.3.) and UJ/CJ practice among UX designers (3.2.4.). For the latter two, we also aim to observe their notation of user- and customer journeys. Taking the elements of our scope, we define the following case study research questions (CSRQs):

CSRQ1. *What terminology is used at ContextMSP?*

CSRQ2. *How do architects and UX designers communicate at ContextMSP?*

CSRQ3. *How do architects of ContextMSP apply UJ/CJ maps in their daily practice?*

CSRQ4. *How do UX designers of ContextMSP apply UJ/CJ maps in their daily practice?*

For selecting the subjects, *convenience sampling* was used: current responsibilities and activities of employees were compared to the topics covered in the CSRQs above. This led to an architect that is active in creating a CJ framework for ContextMSP, hence we chose this architect for CSRQ1; to examine the terminology at ContextMSP. As the framework is meant for architects, and the architect appeared to be active in collaborating with UX, the same expert was selected for CSRQ2 and CSRQ3. For investigating the UX perspective, two UX designers were chosen. One UX designer was active in collaborating with architects, and thus selected for CSRQ2. The other UX designer was a lead UX designer, active in creating journeys and determining standards for creating them. Hence, this UX designer was chosen for CSRQ4. Research techniques used in this case study are interviews (informal and semi-formal), observation and document analysis.

The interview results were processed the same way as we did with JourneySoftware. During the interview, the answers of the interviewee were directly noted and summarized and checked by the interviewee after the interview. There are memo's available of the conversations (just to be certain), but they were unnecessary. For future research, these recordings could be of use (please contact the author in case of interest).

2.2. UJ/CJ Terminology

Just like at JourneySoftware, we also investigated the used concepts at ContextMSP. Getting an overview of what elements are common will later help us evaluating the initial requirements for the artefact. For investigating the used UJ/CJ terminology at ContextMSP (CSRQ1), the list of concepts from our literature study was presented to the architect. By reading the concepts and definitions, the expert marked on a checklist which concepts are applied at ContextMSP. When filling in the checklist, the expert noticed some

concepts are practised/applied at ContextMSP, while the concept is not used. Hence, the checklist was split into two columns: *Concept used* and *Concept applied in practice*. The investigation of concepts can be found in Appendix B.1., and results into the overview of used concepts at ContextMSP shown in Table 2.

Table 2: UJ/CJ concepts recognized and applied at ContextMSP

Concepts used at ContextMSP							
General concept	Concept used	Applied in practice	Comments	Journey specific Concept	Concept used	Applied in practice	Comments
User journey		X	Used at UX Design	Touchpoint	X	**	Main component!
Customer journey	X	X	100% used. Important!	Moment of truth	X	X	Used at UX Design
Buyer journey		X		Deviation		X	Alternative/Exception
Mapping		X		Breakpoint			
User journey map		X	Used at UX Design	Initiator		X	Always a customer
Customer journey map	X	X		Trigger	X	X	Event (as trigger)
Buyer journey map		X	Started recently	Goal	X	X	
Journey concept	X	X		Time			
Planned journey		X		Timeline	X	X	
Actual journey		X		Stage		X	Process used as stage
Scenario				Channel	X	X	
Persona	X	X		Trace			
				Experience	X		Used at UX Design
				Note			
				Opportunity			
				Lens			

Starting with the *general concepts*, the concept terms do not seem to be used at ContextMSP. However, almost every general concept is applied in UJ/CJ context, except for *scenarios*. Customer journeys are well recognised at ContextMSP. According to the architect, they seem to play a big role across different business functions and departments. Customer journey maps help ContextMSP understand customers or potential customers, and meet their needs given their context. The concept “user journey” is not used at ContextMSP. Though, user journey maps do seem to be applied at UX design. UX design uses user journey maps to improve the digital experience, but (incorrectly) calls them “customer journey maps”. Furthermore, ContextMSP is active in specifying buyer journeys, actual journeys and planned journeys.

Compared to the general concepts, *journey specific concepts* seem to be recognized and applied less in practice. Touchpoint, deviation, initiator, trigger, goal, timeline, stage and channels seem to be applied elements. Moment of truth and experience is not used among architects but seems to be practised at UX design. Touchpoint is marked with a “**” sign as it is a special case. When discussing the definition of a touchpoint, the semantics seem to be different than the definition from our study of concepts; “*an instance of interaction with a service provider*” [2]. According to the architect, a touchpoint is a *container of multiple interaction steps (activities) happening on a channel*. In case a journey would remain at a single channel, all steps will still count as one single touchpoint. Only when switching to a different channel during the journey will trigger a new touchpoint.

2.3. UJ/CJ among architects

For investigating the collaboration between UX designers and architects (CSRQ2) and user/customer journey maps from the perspective of the architects (CSRQ3), an interview was held with an architect of ContextMSP. The architect was active in creating a customer journey framework for ContextMSP. The interview protocol (and answers) can be found in Appendix B.2, and covered the following topics:

- Current communication/collaboration between UX and architects (CSRQ4)
- Customer- vs user journeys (CSRQ1)
- How architects create user/customer journey maps (CSRQ2)
- The customer journey framework (CSRQ2)

Collaboration between UX and Architects

Architects seem to collaborate with UX designers in terms of giving advise from a technical point of view. Architects mostly help UX designers optimize *customer flows* to help improve a system or feature, thus customer flows are used as a means for communication between both fields. To create these customer flows, free format is used: simple, informal models without rules to follow. The use of free format creates a major issue in the collaboration between UX designers and architects: meetings become exhaustive as a lot of time is spent at iteratively explaining concepts, models and semantics to reach mutual understanding. The architect added that there is a need for a universal language and sees a potency in the use of user-/customer journeys in this collaboration.

User-/customer journey maps among architects

Discussing the user/customer journey practice, architects seem to be only active in making *planned customer journeys*. Architects seem to create them in two formats:

1. Customer journey map in free format
2. Customer journey map in Archimate, using the Customer Journey Framework

Customer journeys in free format

To illustrate the use of free format customer journeys, an example was provided by the architect, shown in Figure 3. The example shows a planned customer journey for acquiring a savings account. As identified in 3.2.2., ContextMSP has a different perspective on the semantics of a touchpoint. Here we see that multiple activities can be contained in a touchpoint, depending on whether there is a switch from channel to channel. This is due to ContextMSP is focused on supporting omnichannel journeys; continuous synchronous journeys across different channels (previously discussed in 3.1.3.).

Figure 3: Customer journey example among architects, created in free format

By discussing the customer journey example, the architect brought up three current issues around customer journey maps at ContextMSP:

1. *Where does the customer journey start and end?*
2. *How can the customer journey be separated into sub journeys?*
3. *Are external steps also part of the customer journey?*

The answer to the first two questions remains in the *abstraction level*: whether the journey should be detailed or high-level (depending on the purpose). Although the abstraction level is not in the list of concepts from our literature study, there seems to be a **practical need** to have an abstraction level determined for each journey. To answer the third question, it would be best to leave external customer journey steps out of scope. According to our literature study, customer journeys are merely about the interactions between service provider and customer, and the experience that comes with it.

Customer journeys in Archimate

At ContextMSP, customer journeys are also made in architecture to show the architectural components related to a customer journey. For this, ContextMSP uses Archimate and a customer journey architecture framework developed by ContextMSP. The customer journey framework is meant to provide structure for architects for modelling customer journeys in Archimate. The original framework can be found in Appendix B.2. The framework is specifically focused on sales architecture, used in *Project Start Architectures* (PSAs) when something new is introduced but still needs to be connected to current architecture. To clarify the framework, we have added the Archimate layers to the framework which is shown in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: CJ framework (from ContextMSP)

The framework consists of four layers, all sublayers of the Archimate business layer. The four layers are *Customer event* (1), *Customer journey* (2), *Module* (3) and *Data Master* (4). The layers are structured in a way that each layer creates business services that support the layer above. Figure 73 in appendix B.2. provides an example of how the framework can be applied to architecture. To clarify this example (as the architecture example is extensive), an abstract version is made and shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: customer journey example(simplified) among architects, created in Archimate

The example in Figure 5 shows the architecture of the customer journey: *Selling a savings account* (customer journey layer). The request for a savings account is triggered by a separation of a customer from its partner (customer event layer). A divorce or separation can trigger a customer's mind to start saving study money for their children when they are older. The customer journey, modelled as a service, is enabled by Payment/Savings request management and supported by *Relation management* (module layer). Relationship management is responsible for onboarding natural persons (NPs). Subsequently, the onboarding process is supported by *Relation data administration* (Data master layer), using application services of the CRM system.

Further analysing this customer journey map, we see that this is a new way of specifying customer journeys compared to our literature study. Instead of taking the customers perspective, the processes are written from the companies' perspective, such as "inform customer" rather than "receive notification". Additionally, elements discussed in the journey examples of part 2.4. and 3.1. (such as channels, stages, touchpoints, experience or flow between the CJ elements) seem to be absent from this customer journey notation. The customer journey layer seems to merely focus on showing the structure of architectural elements: what architectural elements support a specific customer journey. Using this view, both sales and architects can directly see what processes, functions and employees are involved in the realisation of a specific customer journey.

2.4. UJ/CJ among UX designers

To further investigate the collaboration between UX designers and architects (CSRQ2) an interview was held with a UX designer (UX interviewee 1) that actively collaborates with architects of ContextMSP. To examine the user/customer journey maps from the UX perspective (CSRQ4), an interview was held with a lead UX design (UX interviewee 2). The UX interview protocol, answers and notes can be found in Appendix B.3. The interview covered the following topics:

- Current communication/collaboration between UX and architects (CSRQ4)
- Customer- vs user journeys (CSRQ1)
- How UX designers create user/customer journey maps (CSRQ3)

Collaboration between UX and Architects

From the UX perspective, UX designers collaborate with architects to discuss UX proposals and UX deliverables. Architects seem to complement UX designers with a bird-side view and a technical view. When creating visual- and interaction designs, UX designers want to ensure their creations and solutions are technically feasible, thus asking architects for technical impact analysis. For communicating UX ideas with architects, UX designers use *customer flows* and *interaction models*. Complete examples of customer flows and an interaction model can be found in Appendix B.3. To give an impression, Figure 6 contains snapshots of the examples.

Figure 6: Customer flows (left) and interaction model (right)

Journey maps are not used in the communication between UX designer and architects, although the interviewee saw great potency to use it as a means to communicate. He adds that there is a condition for introducing the use of journey maps in this matter: there needs to be additional time available to create and discuss the journeys.

User/customer journey maps among UX designers

Discussing user/customer journey maps, UX designers seem to merely speak of *user journeys* but only talk in terms of *customer journeys*. When discussing the differences, it appears they create *planned user journey maps* and *planned customer journey maps*. Where user journeys are used for improving a specific system, for example, a part of an app, customer journeys are used for a holistic view that includes multiple channels. At UX design the experience is either the expected experience or experience measured from market research. Previously, UX designers created customer journeys using Sketch, only following some predefined rules on how to create the journeys. However, the creation of customer journeys is now further standardized by using Smaply instead of Sketch. Where Sketch still gave UX designers some freedom in how to create journeys, Smaply has a predefined format to create journeys with. Thus, two customer journey maps have been observed and discussed:

1. Customer journey map created with Sketch (old way)
2. Customer journey map created with Smaply (new way)

The complete customer journey maps can be found in Appendix B.3. In the following sections, we discuss and examine the example a part of the customer journey maps (as the full journey maps are extensive).

Customer journey in Sketch (Partly free format)

The first example is shown in Figure 24. It is a customer journey of buying a house (with the help of a bank), created in Sketch. The customer flow is shown from left to right. The X-axis serves as a time frame in which the journey takes place. On top of the journey, *stages* are represented (both high-level and low-level stages), and the *experience* is represented with emoticons as well as the height of the emoticons on the Y-axis (under, on or above the 'neutral' emotion line). The experience is measured through a market research with customers. *Thoughts*, a new concept compared to our established list of concepts, are represented through dialogue balloons. *Activities* are represented in text with squares around them. The *channels* are linked to the activity, each given its own symbol. Additionally, *moment of truth* and *pain points* are represented by chosen symbols. *Pain points* are a new concept, which represents an issue-to-solve in a journey. When asking where the interviewee saw the touchpoints, she answered to see the activities linked to a channel as a touchpoint, since those are the moments the customer interacts with ContextMSP.

Figure 7: Customer journey example among UX designers (old notation)

Customer journey in Smaply (Smaply format)

The other example is the customer journey in the current UX format, created with Smaply. The customer journey of a *persona* named Fadil, is shown in Figure 8. On top of the journey map, the customer *goal* is shown. The *stages* are visualised on the X-axis at the top of the journey, and the *experience* is represented by emoticons, as well as placing the emoticon on a specific height of the Y-axis. The *channels* are once shown by swim lanes and symbols corresponding to the channel. Additional elements are *quotes*, *idea's and tips* and *pain points*. Pain points were already identified as new elements in the Sketch example, as well as thoughts which are similar to quotes here. Idea's and tips sound new but actually represent opportunities and are therefore not seen as a new element. As the last element, we see a *backstage lane*. Although empty, this lane is created for a reason: implement technical/architectural information. This implicates that Smaply believes that UX designers should also think about technical aspects. They already created some sort of link between UX and architects, acknowledging the necessity to link both fields (the main motive of this thesis).

Figure 8: Customer journey example among UX designers (new notation)

An interesting comment by the second interviewee was that she was a bit frustrated that the term journey is starting to be used everywhere within ContextMSP, while many of these journeys do not even include experience. According to the interviewee, this is the main component what separates a journey from a scenario or customer flow. Hence, experience is seen as a must in our requirement list in 3.4.

2.5. Conclusion - Case study

In this case study, we examined ContextMSP to investigate their current user-/customer journey practice and the collaboration between UX designers and architects. We focused on four topics: The user-/customer journey terminology (CSRQ1), communication and collaboration between architects and UX designers (CSRQ2), and the current UJ/CJ practice among architects (CSRQ3) and UX design (CSRQ4).

- CSRQ 1** When analysing the terminology, we saw that most UJ/CJ general concepts and specific elements are applied in practice although the name of the concept is not always used. User journeys are created at UX design and buyer journeys are created at marketing, but both are just called customer journeys at ContextMSP. We also saw in the UX example that personas are actually part of a customer journey as well. Touchpoint seems to have a different meaning at ContextMSP: here a touchpoint is seen as a container of multiple *activities* in one *channel*. Though UX designers did not even use touchpoints, but used activities and channels instead.
- CSRQ 2** Examining the collaboration between UX designers and architects (CSRQ2), architects apparently complement UX designers with their holistic- and technical viewpoint. Architects analyse whether new ideas or changes from UX designers are technically feasible with the current architecture/technology. Additionally, architects have a "bird's eye view" that helps UX designers see things more globally, for example looking at the pre-purchase, purchase, and post-purchase phase. When communicating, the two fields seem to discuss customer flows and interaction models. When collaborating, customer flows and interaction models, as well as free format models are used. Journey maps are not yet used although the interviewees (both UX designers and the architect) saw great potency in using journey maps as well.
- CSRQ 3** Investigating UJ/CJ practice among architects, we saw architects only create customer journeys, made in *free format (tool of choice)* or in *architecture (Archimate)*. To create the customer journey in Archimate, a customer journey architecture framework was created showing the relations between elements. Although it sounds like ContextMSP is also relating customer journeys to architecture, just like the aim of our thesis, both are very different. Instead of connecting a customer journey to architecture (the aim of this thesis), ContextMSP's architectural customer journeys *only show the architectural parts* involved in a specific customer journey, still missing the journey itself. Additionally, both customer journey examples miss many common customer journey elements. *Experience, channels* and *stages* were all not present although these are common elements of a customer journey.
- CSRQ 4** At last, we investigated UJ/CJ practice among UX designers. UX designers also seem to only speak of customer journeys but happen to create both user- and customer journeys. As examples, we observed two customer journey examples. One was party free format (made in Sketch), while the other was compliant to the format of the tool it was created with (Smapply). These journeys are more representative of the examples discussed in the literature (2.4), and most elements were common to our list of journey specific elements. The UX customer journeys even add two new elements to our list: *thoughts* (shown as quotes) and *pain points*. Thoughts represent what the customer thinks at a certain moment, while pain points are issues in the journey, indicating where and how a journey can be improved.

3. Summary

In this chapter we examined how user- and customer journeys are applied in practice, complementing the literature study results with insights from a practical viewpoint. To do this, we held an in-depth interview with an actual customer journey software vendor anonymized as JourneySoftware (Chapter 1) and performed a case study at ContextMSP, an MSP in the banking domain (Chapter 2). To find out to what extent user journey maps are supported and applied (SQ1), we complement the literature study results by examining the types of journeys (SQ1.1), the elements of a journey (SQ1.2) and the current ways how user journeys are specified (SQ1.3). Additionally, this time we also investigated how user journeys are supported and applied in the fields of UX design and enterprise architecture (SQ1.4).

SQ 1.1 As types of journeys, JourneySoftware supports actual customer journeys, were aware of planned journeys (although they do not support it), but unaware of user journeys and buyer journeys. The results of ContextMSP on this matter were similar, they create and speak of planned journeys, actual journeys and customer journeys, but do not recognize buyer journeys and user journeys. However, when explaining these journeys, buyer journeys seems to be applied at Marketing for new customer acquisition, and user journeys seem to be used a lot at UX design to improve the UX of a system. The results journey types recognized and applied can be found on the left in Table 3.

Table 3: Recognized and applied General- and journey specific concepts (JourneySoftware + ContextMSP)

General concepts	Case study		Expert interview	Journey specific Concepts	Case study		Expert Interview
	ContextMSP		JourneySoftware		ContextMSP		JourneySoftware
	Concept used	Applied in practice	Term used & applied practice		Concept used	Applied in practice	Term used & applied practice
User journey		X		Persona	X	X	X
Customer journey	X	X	X	Touchpoint	X	X	X
Buyer journey		X	X	Moment of truth	X	X	X
Mapping		X		Deviation		X	
User journey map		X		Breakpoint			X
Customer journey map	X	X	X	Initiator		X	
Buyer journey map		X		Trigger	X	X	X
Journey concept	X	X		Goal	X	X	X
Planned journey		X		Time			X
Actual journey		X	X	Timeline	X	X	X
Scenario				Stage		X	X
				Channel	X	X	X
				Trace			
				Experience	X	X	X
				Note			
				Opportunity			X
				Lens			

An interesting result about actual customer journeys is that it does not seem to be applied in the fields of architects and UX design. JourneySoftware does not see their software applied in those fields as most clients use it for customer service and marketing. Additionally, all examples discussed in the interviews of ContextMSP were planned journeys. Due to this result, we are more likely to shape our artefact in scoping on static, planned journeys instead of dynamic, actual journeys.

SQ 1.2 The practical investigation results of user/customer journey concepts are also shown in Table 3. We saw that UX designers at ContextMSP use a persona in a journey map, thus persona has been moved to the journey specific concepts. Table 3 also allows us to see which concepts JourneySoftware and ContextMSP have common: touchpoint, moment of truth, trigger, goal, timeline, stage (although differently named) channel and experience. Further, we see that ContextMSP recognises/applies Deviation and Initiator to their journey map, and that JourneySoftware applies Opportunity. These insights will play a role in our Treatment Design, helping us to select the elements for our artefact.

Additional to the Journey specific elements defined in our literature study, the practical investigation has lead to new elements: *Thoughts, abstraction level, pain points*. For the architect, there is a need to have an abstraction level defined to determine the level of detail of a journey. Additionally, experience has become a must-have due to one UX interviewees being frustrated that people start to use journey on everything similar to a flow chart.

One issue raised when touchpoint was discussed as concept. The definition of JourneySoftware and ContextMSP seemed different from our definition. As we defined touchpoint as “An interaction between customer and service provider” [2], Both ContextMSP and JourneySoftware sees touchpoint as synonym to a channel; a mechanism that enables interactions rather than the interactions themselves. UX designers at ContextMSP did not speak of touchpoints linked activities to channels. The architect on the other hand said he saw a touchpoint of a session of multiple activities on a specific channel. In [3] the difference is clarified, stating that a touchpoint is enabled by a channel, such as booking a table (Touchpoint) through an app(channel), and that booking a table is a high-level process consisting multiple activities. Hence the confusion is now solved: a touchpoint is a high-level process that can be subdivided into lower-level activities and is enabled by a channel.

SQ 1.3 We also examined current ways of specifying user journeys. As user journey maps are hard to find, we mainly investigated customer journeys instead of user journeys. In the literature, we examined existing frameworks and methods that can be used to map user- and customer journeys as well as multiple user- and customer journey examples in section 2.4. In the practical investigation, we evaluated a customer journey example from JourneySoftware and multiple customer journey examples from ContextMSP. As a result, observed elements and visualisations are taken into consideration as initial requirements for our artefact.

SQ 1.4 At last, we investigated how user journey maps are currently supported and applied in the fields of UX design and enterprise architecture. In the interview with JourneySoftware, we saw that actual journeys are not commonly applied within these fields. At ContextMSP, we analysed multiple planned customer journey examples and found that customer journeys created by architects are quite different from the ones made by UX designers. Architects seem to use free format or use their architectural language Archimate to create journeys. UX designers seem to create journeys in the predefined format of Smaply, which is their customer journey design tool. The UX design customer journeys contained significantly more elements that were defined in our list of Journey Specific Elements. Architects do not seem to use things like channels, stages or experience, which could be due to the high-level perspective architects have compared to the detailed view of UX designers. Furthermore, UX designers and architects seem to collaborate in the way that architects complement UX designers with a holistic view and a technical view. When communicating with one another, they only use customer flows and interaction models. All interviewees at ContextMSP saw great use in using journeys to communicate with one another.

4. References

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APPENDIX A: Expert interview -JourneySoftware

*** As the interview was held in Dutch, the interview protocol and answers are Dutch as well. During the interview, the answers of the interviewee were directly written down and summarized, resulting in the documented answers below.*

Vooraf

- Bedanken voor de komst.
- Mijzelf introduceren
- Vragen of de interviewee zichzelf en zijn functie binnen JourneySoftware wilt introduceren
- Vragen of het gesprek opgenomen mag worden

Algemeen

1. In mijn literatuuronderzoek is naar voren gekomen dat er verschil wordt gemaakt tussen
 1. Customer en user journeys
 2. Actual en Planned journeys (tevens Dynamisch vs statisch)

Zijn alle vier de termen bij jullie bekend? welke worden ondersteund door JourneySoftware?

focus op CJ, in het specifiek: actual customer journeys. Werken wel samen met planned journeys want dat is een interessante koppeling: Top down vs bottom up (bottom up belangrijker want context wordt belangrijker). Ondanks dat wij bottom-up werken wilt de klant ook dingen blijven plannen. We werken dus met partners zoals Salesforce samen (zitten in planned journeys, prog: Journeybuilder). Ze hebben een integratiegebouwd met journeybuilder. Inbound en outbound bij elkaar, uniek volgens hem.

2. Hoe creëert JourneySoftware real-time customer journeys? (Welke Technieken + Data)

One houdt per persoon dat bij. Is organisatorisch niet de doen-> personas gebruiken. Al journey gemapt? (aan bedrijf vragen). Wat voor activiteiten in zo 'n journey. User journey niet belangrijk hangt.

Data: Gedragsdata van nu (Waar klikken ze op, wat vragen ze). Alleen de voorgecategoriseerde data(filter). Uit backbone systemen van klant. Context staat centraal (wat is de klant op dit moment aan het doen).

Bi: waar zitten bottlenecks, gaan mensen heen of terug?

Ai: Wat gaan we ermee doen? Wat is de beste journey, huidige kennis van journeys en dan daarop inspelen (een gele website gevne ipv rode. Journey based decisioning) -> Next best conversation. Gaat om welke stap je toeschuift om een klant op een punt/goal te krijgen.

Toepassingen van CJM in de praktijk

3. Uit literatuur is gebleken dat het hoofddoel van user journeys om user experience te begrijpen (1), te evalueren(2) en te verbeteren (3). Jullie noemen als hoofddoel het verbeteren van engagement. Zie jij hier overeenkomst of verschil tussen deze hoofddoelen?

Experience: hoe maak ik dit proces mee . Engagement is meer hoe van hoe kan ik jou triggeren om te blijven op langere termijn, wordt er écht geluisterd naar de klant. Wordt er naar mij geluisterd. Omdat dit blijft doorgaan is engagement eigenlijk een constant toenemende/lerende relatie.

4. Uit literatuuronderzoek blijkt dat CJM vooral gebruikt wordt om
 1. Een dienst product of dienst te ontwerpen of verbeteren.
 2. Experience journeys optimaliseren

3. Een klant zover te krijgen dat hij/zij jouw product koopt (3) (buyer journey).
Komt dit overeen met het gebruik van JourneySoftware?

*Alle 3 absoluut. Bij punt 2 wel een toevoeging: zowel voor de klant als voor het bedrijf optimaliseren.
Verder 2 trends die wij zien:
- Vroeger was het meer cross/upsell, nu meer: waar heeft de klant behoefte aan.
- Begon met marketing/niet pushen, naar klant luisteren -> maar nu (onze visie) zouden eigenlijk alle afdelingen ermee bezig moeten zijn.*

5. Jullie doelen heb ik gemapt op de doelen uit de literatuur.

Acquisitie	Buyer journey (3)
Onboarding	Journeys optimaliseren (1)
Servicing	Diensten optimaliseren (2)
Retention	Customers houden
Advocacy	Customers houden
LTV	Huidige meer of grotere producten laten kopen/gebruiken

Ben je het eens met de volgende mapping op literatuur? Hoe verschillen Advocacy en Retention?

*LTV = lifetimevalue (kan ik de klant langdurig klant houden)
Acquisitie = overhalen om te kopen.
Advocacy eigen klanten als ambassadeurs.
Onboarding= iemand die al klant is helpen met de eerste stapjes.*

6. Volgens literatuur zijn er 3 velden die CJ/UJ mapping gebruiken:

1. Marketing
2. Enterprise architects/business architects (vormgeven van diensten/informatie/architectuur)
3. UX design

Ziet u deze 3 velden ook terug in uw klanten?

Horen Acquisitie, onboarding, servicing, retention, Advocacy en LTV allemaal bij deze categorieën?

*Customerservice mist in de rij. Interne optimalisatie mist ook. (interne diensten)
Maar wij zien vooral Marketing en customerservice.*

7. Wat is volgens jou de huidige status van customer journey tool support? Jullie concurrentie?

*Op gebied van actual journeys zijn wij de enige. Planned journeys, een hoop. Er zijn wel veel partijen die data verzamelen en BI erop loslaten. Maar echt de journeys shapen.
Journey analyse en Journey orchestration.*

Nieuw vergeleken met literatuur

8. Op jullie site staat dat JourneySoftware met AI en predictive models klantgedrag voorspelt, hoe gaat dat in zn werk? Wordt dit veel gebruikt?

*Diensten toeschuiven. Ook: verbeteren van journeys door automatische optimalisatie.
Ze gaan oplossingen vergelijken en suggereert dus de beste dienst/verbetering om de flow beter te laten lopen. Dat baseert hij op voormalig gedrag van journeys. Dit wordt nog maar weinig gebruikt, deep learning staat nog in de kinderschoenen. Ook is adoptie hierin (in markt) nog laag. Mensen willen zelf die controle houden.*

9. Jullie noemen jullie touchpoints Omni-channel ipv multichannel (uit literatuur). Kan je dit verschil uitleggen? Geldt dit voor alle touchpoints en services?

Omnichannel: ipv ik kan communiceren via verschillende kanalen(multichannel). Omni = ik kan het gecoördineert doen. Het ene kanaal gaat verder met waar je in het andere kanaal gebleven was. Dit gaat dus compleet gecoördineerd. Wij zijn eigenlijk een soort hub tussen verschillende kanalen. Uitleg: Met ids koppelen ze journeys, onthouden ze waar ze zijn: wordt automatisch gesynchroniseerd. Vergt integratie van kanalen van het bedrijf maar is niet heel veel werk (gemiddeld 2 dagen). Integratie is

makkelijk omdat we een onafhankelijk kanaal zijn. Wij zijn gebouwd om te integreren, de software dient eigenlijk als een hub.

Used concepts

10. Qua gebruikte termen/elementen vond ik deze lijst. Gebruiken jullie ook andere termen?

{ Lifecycle Stage } a phase in the customer journey

{ Proposition } a product or service the customer is interested in

{ Activity Type } what the customer is doing

{ Interaction } what a customer is looking at

{ Channel/Touchpoint } where a customer is engaging with the brand

Figure 9: Terminology ppt slide of JourneySoftware

Zoja, Kunt u aankruisen welke bij u nog meer bekend zijn?

Voor onze structuur is dit het belangrijkste. Touchpoint gebruiken wij maar met een andere betekenis. wij kennen 6 kanalen: Web app, fysiek, assisted(callcentre) en social en outbound. Touchpoints zijn dan voor ons Website 1 website 2. Outbound heeft bv als touchpoints: fax, email en brieven.

General concepts			
Wordt gebruikt?	Term	Synonym(s)	Definition
	User journey	User experience journey	Story about an individual's actions, feelings, perceptions, and frame of mind including the positive, negative, and neutral moments as he or she interacts with a product or service over a period of time (Hannington & Martin, 2012)
✓	Customer journey	Customer experience journey	Customer's multi-channel experience and interactions with one or more service providers to achieve a specific goal (Halvorsrud et al., 2016; Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
✓	Buyer journey	Decision funnel	Customer decisions and experiences that show the movement of customers towards purchase of a product of service (Lemon & Verhoef, 2016)
	Mapping	Journey mapping	Tracking and describing user/customer experiences when using a product or service, and depicting it on a flow diagram (Bernard & Andritsos, 2017; Maguire, 2013)
	User journey map	User experience journey, User journey map	Visualization of experiences people have when interacting with a product or service by using a system (Hannington & Martin, 2012) <i>maguire</i>
✓	Customer journey map		Visualisation Customer's experience and interactions with one or more service providers to achieve a specific goal (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
	Buyer journey map	Decision funnel, path-to-purchase model	Models of customer decisions and experiences to guide customers towards purchase of a product of service (Lemon & Verhoef, 2016)
	Journey concept		A journey in development, but still conceptual (Norton & Pine, 2013)
	Planned journey	Expected journey, Ideal journey, Retrospective Maps	Hypothetical, static journey reflecting the service delivery process (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
✓	Actual journey	Prospective Maps	Individual, dynamic journey that occurs during execution of a service (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
	Scenario		A set of ordered user/customer actions, used to create user journeys (Hannington & Martin, 2012)
✓	Persona		Representation of a typical customer that contains motivations, goals, painpoints and other characteristics (Signavio, 2018).

Figure 10: Used general UJ/CJ concepts by JourneySoftware

Journey specific elements			
Wordt gebruikt?	Term	Synonym(s)	Definition
X	Touchpoint	Service encounter, Communication channel, Contact point, Service event, Service moment	An interaction (instance of communication) between customer and service provider (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
✓	Moment of truth	Key moment	Decision points that can make or break the success of the journey. It can be a simple decision, or a hard decision that is experienced as a barrier (Signavio, 2018)
	Deviation		Touchpoints from where the path goes different than what was planned (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
drive off	Breakpoint	Drop-off	Moment where the journey stops (Hobbs et al., 2013)
	Initiator		Initiator of a touchpoint, can be a customer/user, service provider or subcontractor (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
✓	Trigger	Start, starting point	Trigger of the customer journey, either an idea or demand (Signavio, 2018)
✓	Goal	Outcome	The thing what the customer aims to achieve, such as obtaining a loan in a banking context, this is the final touchpoint of a service (Signavio, 2018)
✓	Time		Time when a touchpoint is encountered by the customer (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
✓	Timeline		Duration of the journey from the starting touchpoint to the final touchpoint. The timeline can be depicted by actual time, or ordering touchpoints by giving them numbers (Bernard & Andritsos 2017)
✓	Stage		Container of multiple touchpoints (Bernard & Andritsos 2017)
✓	Channel	Customer channel, Service interface	A medium for users and service providers to interact with one another (Sousa & Voss, 2006) serving as a mediator of a touchpoint (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
	Trace		Content that emerges as result of a touchpoint (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
✓	Experience	Feeling	Emotions (i), emotions scale (ii) and customer quotes (iii) (Bernard & Andritsos 2017)
	Note	Banner, Text	Comments that contain important textual information about the journey map (Signavio, 2018)
✓	Opportunity	Improvement	Touchpoint to improve (Lankhorst, 2017)
	Lens		Grouping touchpoints to a certain context or domain, while excluding the other touchpoints (Bernard & Andritsos 2017)

Figure 11: Journey specific UJ/CJ concepts used by JourneySoftware

Notatie

11. De volgende afbeelding (Figure 69) is een screenshot van een realtime customer journey die gegenereerd is door JourneySoftware. Kunt u de elementen uitleggen?

Figure 12: Screenshot of JourneySoftware

12. Wat zijn volgens u de hoofdeisen waar een nieuwe modelleertaal van user/customer journeys aan moet voldoen?

Ga je naar de actual journeys kijken, dan moet het een open taal zijn omdat integratie een hoofdeis is.

APPENDIX B: Case study: ContextMSP

** As the interviews were held in Dutch, the interview protocols and answers are Dutch as well. During the interview, the answers of the interviewee were directly written down and summarized, resulting in the documented answers below.

B.1. Interview: UJ/CJ concepts

Welke termen gebruiken jullie ook volgens de bijbehorende definitie?(Kruis aan met een 'X'). Indien een term gebruikt wordt maar met andere betekenis, geef het dan een sterretje ('*') en leg uit wat er anders is.

General concepts			
Wordt gebruikt?	Term	Synonym(s)	Definition
	User journey	User experience journey	Story about an individual's actions, feelings, perceptions, and frame of mind-including the positive, negative, and neutral moments as he or she interacts with a product or service over a period of time (Hannington & Martin, 2012)
X	Customer journey	Customer experience journey	Customer's multi-channel experience and interactions with one or more service providers to achieve a specific goal (Halvorsrud et al., 2016; Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
X	Buyer journey	Decision funnel	Customer decisions and experiences that show the movement of customers towards purchase of a product of service (Lemon & Verhoef, 2016)
X	Mapping	Journey mapping	Tracking and describing user/customer experiences when using a product or service, and depicting it on a flow diagram (Bernard & Andritsos, 2017; Maguire, 2013)
X	User journey map	User experience journey, User journey map	Visualization of experiences people have when interacting with a product or service by using a system (Hannington & Martin, 2012)
X	Customer journey map		Visualisation Customer's experience and interactions with one or more service providers to achieve a specific goal (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
X	Buyer journey map	Decision funnel, path-to-purchase model	Models of customer decisions and experiences to guide customers towards purchase of a product of service (Lemon & Verhoef, 2016)
X	Journey concept		A journey in development, but still conceptual (Norton & Pine, 2013)
X	Planned journey	Expected journey, Ideal journey, Retrospective Maps	Hypothetical, static journey reflecting the service delivery process (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
X	Actual journey	Prospective Maps	Individual, dynamic journey that occurs during execution of a service (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
	Scenario		A set of ordered user/customer actions, used to create user Journeys (Hannington & Martin, 2012)
X	Persona		Representation of a typical customer that contains motivations, goals, painpoints and other characteristics (Signavio, 2018).

Figure 13: General UJ/CJ concepts used by ContextMSP

Journey specific elements			
Wordt gebruikt?	Term	Synonym(s)	Definition
X	Touchpoint	Service encounter, Communication channel, Contact point, Service event, Service moment	An interaction (instance of communication) between customer and service provider (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
X	Moment of truth	Key moment	Decision points that can make or break the success of the journey. It can be a simple decision, or a hard decision that is experienced as a barrier (Signavio, 2018)
	Deviation		Touchpoints from where the path goes different than what was planned (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
	Breakpoint	Drop-off	Moment where the journey stops (Hobbs et al., 2013)
	Initiator		Initiator of a touchpoint, can be a customer/user, service provider or subcontractor (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
X	Trigger	Start, starting point	Trigger of the customer journey, either an idea or demand (Signavio, 2018)
X	Goal	Outcome	The thing what the customer aims to achieve, such as obtaining a loan in a banking context, this is the final touchpoint of a service (Signavio, 2018)
	Time		Time when a touchpoint is encountered by the customer (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
X	Timeline		Duration of the journey from the starting touchpoint to the final touchpoint. The timeline can be depicted by actual time, or ordering touchpoints by giving them numbers (Bernard & Andritsos 2017)
	Stage		Container of multiple touchpoints (Bernard & Andritsos 2017)
X	Channel	Customer channel, Service interface	A medium for users and service providers to interact with one another (Sousa & Voss, 2006) serving as a mediator of a touchpoint (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
	Trace		Content that emerges as result of a touchpoint (Halvorsrud et al., 2016)
X	Experience	Feeling	Emotions (i), emotions scale (ii) and customer quotes (iii) (Bernard & Andritsos 2017)
	Note	Banner, Text	Comments that contain important textual information about the journey map (Signavio, 2018)
	Opportunity	Improvement	Touchpoint to improve (Lankhorst, 2017)
	Lens		Grouping touchpoints to a certain context or domain, while excluding the other touchpoints (Bernard & Andritsos 2017)

Figure 14: General UJ/CJ concepts used by ContextMSP

Notes regarding: User journeys vs customer journeys

Wij hebben het altijd over customer journeys. Echter denk we bij UX customer journeys als term gebruiken, terwijl we het daar hebben over user journeys.

Touchpoint andere berekening dan theorie: [ContextMSP]: Van moment van begin interactie tot stoppen van de sessie. Als hij alles op 1 channel zou doen, dan zou het hele proces als een touchpoint worden beschouwd. Touchpoints worden aangegeven door de klant. Wanneer een nieuwe sessie begint bij een channel.

B.2. Interview: UJ/CJ maps among architects

Vooraf

- Bedanken voor de komst.
- Mijzelf introduceren
- Vragen of de interviewee zichzelf en zijn functie binnen ContextMSP kan introduceren?
- Vragen of het oké is om het gesprek op te nemen

Mij is vernomen dat u een terminologie heeft vastgesteld rondom user journeys en customer journeys binnen ContextMSP. In dit interview wil ik gaan kijken of deze terminologie overeenkomt met de concepten uit de literatuur. Voordat we naar de vergelijking gaan tussen literatuur en de door u vastgestelde termen, heb ik eerst enkele andere vragen.

Samenwerking UX - EA

1. Hoe is de samenwerking tussen architecten en UX design, en de rol van journeys hierin?

We werken samen met UX op gebied van customer flows uitwerken. Op gebied van journeys? Nee. Nog niet, maar zouden we wel willen. Qua modellen communiceren wij met free format; informele modellen. Er is veel behoefte aan een universele taal op gebied van journeys. Qua meetings zijn we vaan de eerste helft uitleggen van de legenda en hebben we vervolgens de 2^e helft discussie van wat is wat. Iedereen is anders gevormd qua kennis (studie, voormalig werk) of is zelfs onbewust onbekwaam door geen Archimate of Togaf certificaat te hebben.

Customer journey framework

2. Waarvoor wordt het framework gebruikt? (denk aan afdelingen, interne processen, begeleiding bij processen etc)

Deze wordt gebruikt door business- en solution architecten op de afdeling verkoop om customer journeys te maken, gekoppeld aan architectuur van processen en applicaties. Het wordt veel gebruikt bij PSA: project start architectures. Stel er is wat nieuws gemaakt door UX, dan moet het nog gekoppeld worden aan architectuur.

3. Moeten alle gemapte journeys binnen ContextMSP conform jouw termen zijn, of is dit optioneel?

Het dient als standaard, maar wordt nog niet veel gebruikt.

4. Waar kwam het idee of de opdracht vandaan om een terminologie vast te stellen? Ontstond er bijvoorbeeld een verzoek vanuit een probleem binnen ContextMSP?

Dit kwam vanuit een besluit tijdens een meeting. Toen Pega (CRM platform), gekocht werd speelde de vraag op hoe we CJ's flexibel gaan maken. Hierbij is het uiteindelijke doel om vragen en informatie aan de klant voor te schotelen aan de hand van zijn of haar context.

5. Wat was uw aanpak voor het vaststellen van uw terminologie?

De concepten heb ik gekozen op basis van eigen kennis, en kennis verkregen van collega's. We hebben een halfjaar lang zo'n 10 tot 15 meetings gehouden waarin we de terminologie met collega architecten besproken hebben. In het begin was dit met collega architecten binnen de afdeling, maar vervolgens ook met architecten van andere afdelingen.

6. Is er een validatie uitgevoerd op uw set aan termen?

Momenteel ben ik het metamodel aan het valideren. Dit doe ik door met andere architecten uit de modelling guild te gaan zitten; dat is een soort architecten community. We gaan hierbij te werk van abstract niveau naar gedetailleerd niveau. (globale customer journeys naar gedetailleerde journeys).

7. Kunt u het framework uitleggen?

- Framework structureert welke business services ondersteunen welke business services
- Journeylaag: stel je verkoopt een product en je laat een scherm zien met een adres, die klopt niet, dan kan ie dat aanpassen in de module laag.
- In de CJ laag zitten de experts, daar zit de kennis en de business rules. In de customer event staat puur je **keuzemenu**. Het event stuk bevat dus alles wat bij de event komt kijken (alle mogelijkheden, belangrijke zaken)

Figure 15: Customer journey framework of ContextMSP

Figure 16: Customer journey framework applied to architecture

B.3. Interview UJ/CJ among UX designers (Interviewee 1)

Vooraf

- Bedanken voor de komst.
- Mijzelf introduceren
- Vragen of de interviewee zichzelf en zijn functie binnen ContextMSP kan introduceren?
- Vragen of het oké is om het gesprek op te nemen

Momenteel doe ik onderzoek naar hoe user journeys en customer journeys worden gemapt bij ContextMSP. Daarbij kijk ik hoe zowel architecten als UX designers journeys maken, en de huidige rol van journeys in de communicatie tussen de 2 partijen.

User- vs customer journeys

1. Maakt u onderscheid tussen user journeys en customer journeys? User journeys zijn gericht op de digitale experience van een systeem (single channel), customer journeys zijn gericht op de gehele ervaring verspreid over meerdere channels.

Bij UX spreken we alleen van customer journeys. Echter, na jouw uitleg kan ik zeggen dat wij zowel user journeys als customer journeys maken. Voornamelijk richten wij ons op de digitale experience van de app of website, maar we kijken ook regelmatig naar het hollistische plaatje, de pre-fase en voornamelijk de post-fase.

2. Welke word(en) gebruikt door UX?

Zie antwoord hierboven.

Samenwerking UX - EA

3. Op wat voor gebieden of problemen werken UX-ers en architecten samen?

Architecten zijn bezig met het high-level overzicht en het IT perspectief. Zelf vind ik dat UX'ers bewust moeten zijn van de consequenties en mogelijkheden binnen onze IT: Bewust zijn van welke data nodig is, hoe we vragen stellen, welke vormgevingen, positioneren van features met betrekking tot data, welke interactietechnologieën kan ik gebruiken en of dit alles op technisch (architectuur) gebied mogelijk is.

Dit doe ik door modellen en diagrammen ofwel UX voorstellen of UX deliverables te bespreken met architecten en zo te valideren op technisch gebied. Zo krijg je eigenlijk een technische impact analyse op de UX modellen. Het nadeel hiervan is dat dit mij extra tijd kost, wat mede de reden is dat niet elke collega dit doet.

Er heerst behoefte aan betere communicatie voor betere technische impact analyses en om verkeerde interpretatie op onze modellen te voorkomen. Niet elke Uxer werkt samen met architecten, vanuit de UX cultuur is dit nog niet heel gebruikelijk en het kost extra tijd.

4. Wat voor modellen worden hierbij gebruikt?

Als UXers gebruiken wij: Taakdecomposities(Functionaliteit), scenario's, wireframes, customer flows, scherm ontwerpen (hi-fi). Echter als je het hebt over wat gebruikt wordt om met architecten te communiceren, hebben we het over Customer flows en interactiemodellen. Dan kijkt de architect van goh wat jij voorstelt is lastig vanwege dit en dat (vanuit de techniek).

Zie Figuur 17 en Figuur 18.

CC overzichten flow: Creditcard - Jaar - Overzicht

Figure 17: Interaction model example

Happy Flow

Geen klant meer.

Geen gezamenlijke producten.

Product voor aanvang opstellen ODS opgegeven.

product heeft lopend proces (wordt opgegeven/gemuteerd) voor aanvang opstellen ODS #1 - volgens Intentie

product heeft lopend proces (wordt opgegeven/gemuteerd) voor aanvang opstellen ODS #2 - niet volgens intentie

Product wordt na opstellen lijst afgesloten #1

Product wordt na opstellen lijst afgesloten #2

Gebruiker heeft reeds zijn product beoordeeld, maar buiten het ODS

Figure 18: Customer flows

5. Wat is de huidige rol van user/customer journeys in deze samenwerking?

Nihil.

Creating journey maps at UX

6. Ziet u potentie in het gebruik van user/customer journeys voor communicatie met architecten?

*Helemaal voor, maar de kanttekening is dat er tijd voor moet zijn.
Als je alleen een interactiemodel maakt, zonder technische impact analyse of journeys met architecten, dan gaan er gaten zitten op gebied van customer experience of technische realiseerbaarheid.*

7. Zijn er bij UX bepaalde regels, formats of templates om de journeys te maken? Of is het allemaal free format?

Vastleggen van de journeys en het interactiemodel daar is complete vrijheid in. Wij moeten ons houden aan functionaliteiten

8. Kunt u een voorbeeld van een gemaakte journey laten zien en de elementen uitleggen?

- Niet aan toegekomen

B.3. Interview UJ/CJ among UX designers (Interviewee 2)

Vooraf

- Bedanken voor de komst.
- Mijzelf introduceren
- Vragen of de interviewee zichzelf en zijn functie binnen ContextMSP kan introduceren?
- Vragen of het oké is om het gesprek op te nemen

Momenteel doe ik onderzoek naar hoe user journeys en customer journeys worden gemapt bij ContextMSP. Daarbij kijk ik hoe zowel architecten als UX designers journeys maken, en de huidige rol van journeys in de communicatie tussen de 2 partijen.

1. Kunt u een voorbeeld van een gemaakte journey laten zien en de elementen uitleggen?

We maken zowel journeys hoe ze echt zijn en hoe het moet worden. Zo noemen wij dit verschil IST journeys en SOLL journeys. Met die IST ga je kijken van waar zitten de knelpunten, dan ga je daar ideeën genereren IST journey. De tool die we gebruiken is Smaply. We gebruiken een X aantal persona's met basisbehoeften die gebaseerd zijn op een uitgebreid marktonderzoek, en per journey kiezen we een persona. Zelf ben ik overigens van mening dat er veel over journeys wordt gesproken zonder er experience in te doen. Overigens vinden wij dat het niet uit maakt hoe je het visualiseert, als de belangrijke elementen er maar in zitten.

Voor voorbeelden, zie figuur 19 voor de oude notatie en figuur 20 voor de nieuwe notatie.

koop

Figure 19: Customer journeys among UX designers (the old UX format)

JOURNEY MAP

PROJECT

EXPORT DATE

Figure 20: Customer journeys among UX designers (the new UX format)

